

Keyword based Textbook Recommendation System using KNN algorithm

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Abstract- During the last few decades, with the rise of social media objects, web objects and many more, recommender system played a very vital role in this phenomenon. These objects introduced recommender systems and these recommender systems have taken more and more place in current situation. From e-commerce objects to online objects everywhere there exists a recommender model to provide user ease of use and ease of requirement. In a very general way to describe a recommender system they are set of algorithms or algorithms aimed to provide a set of suggestions and relevant information and requirement to the user.

Keywords – Watermarking, Haar Wavelet, DWT, PSNR

I. INTRODUCTION

Recommender systems are treated as very critical object in some industries as they generate huge income to industry by means of providing relevant items accurately and efficiently. There exists a real-time scenario which identifies the importance of recommender system. As a proof a few years ago, Netflix organized a challenge named Netflix prize where the winning point was to create and present a recommender system that produces a far better performance than the existing recommender system of the Netflix and the cash price was fixed to initiation of 1 million dollar for the winner. The purpose of the recommender system is to provide a relevant object for specific user for specific requirement. This existence idea initiated for two more categories of recommender system they are collaborative filtering recommender system and content-based recommender system.

Collaborative filtering is one of the methods to enhance recommender system by past interactions. For example, a user needs to get a recommendation from the model and say the model uses collaborative filtering method. The past interactions are recorded in the form of matrix and this matrix is known as interaction matrix. Each object is mapped with user requirement with past interactions to provide recommendation. The main idea of collaborative filtering is that it makes predictions based on past interactions and with estimated proximities. Collaborative filtering model assumes and finds the closest users from the user of interest and recommend or suggest the most popular object among these set of neighbors.

When it comes only for the recommendation by means of past interactions the model may not be suitable for all set of use cases since the past records are always not stored in all set of use cases it may be uncertain in nature. To resolve this uncertainty content-based recommendation model comes into picture. The main idea is to build a model based on the available features. Content based recommendation model uses additional data about the users or items or objects for providing the recommendation. In the most real-time applications content-based filtering method is used but majorly combination of both content based as well as collaborative filtering methods are used to provide efficient resource recommendation effectively.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Literature survey is mentioned in section II. Proposed algorithm with data flow models are explained in section III. Experimental results are presented in section IV. Conclusion and Future enhancement is provided in section V.

II. RELATED WORK

[1] It comprises of challenges and remedies that arises and needs to be solved when recommender system is initiated for the model. The challenge that arises when there is a collaborative filtering-based recommender model is that if past interactions are not recorded the model building will be complex than the model building with past interactions. This paper proposed problems that are initiated when deep learning methods are used for creation of the recommender model and remedies are discussed to solve the existence to the maximum extent. [2] The paper consists of the survey and roads ahead of news recommender system. [3] Content based recommendation system gathers more information when compared to other filtering methods and provides an efficient recommendation by processing with large amount of data. [4] The major focus was on user reviews. Recommender model was built by considering a unique metric in the form of user reviews. User reviews are recorded and made into use for the suggestion of relevant objects by recommender model. [5] This consists of various text mining techniques for the initial build-up of recommendation engine. Basically, text mining techniques are the processes that transforms unstructured form of data or information into structured form of data or information respectively.

Text mining techniques uses natural language processing which is concerned with the interactions between computers and human language or human understandable language. So, text mining allows machines or computers to understand the human language and process it automatically.

The existing recommendation engines are majorly developed with collaborative filtering methods or content-based filtering. In most of the cases the recommendation engine is built with hybrid nature that is combination of both collaborative filtering and content-based filtering.

There are two types of approaches in collaborative filtering, memory based and model-based approach. Memory based approach is also known to be neighborhood collaborative filtering method. Essentially, ratings of the user item are predicted based on their nearer items or probabilities of neighborhood. This can be further split into two-way pipeline for recommendation engine by providing recommendation by means of items and recommendation by means of user reviews.

Model based approaches are the predictive models for recommendation engine using machine learning and core machine learning concepts. Model based approaches include inner models like decision trees, rule-based approaches, and latent factor models and many more. The main advantage of using collaborative method is that it is simpler to implement and provides high level coverage. Another vital advantage is that it does not require understanding of the object content. The disadvantage is that it's not a friendly recommender that is no interaction of object with the model. This is referred to as the cold start problem.

Memory based algorithms are often known as less efficient in performance since there is a memory metric involved. Content based recommendation engines generate the relevant suggestions to the user by means of their preferences and profile. In Real-time content-based recommendation model uses dynamic and different sources of data to generate recommendation for at most relevancy. The simplest form of the content-based recommendation engine requires item level data source as well as user level data source. This type of model is most advantageous for recommending objects when there is an insufficient amount of data or information available. The disadvantage is that the recommendations are more obvious that is if the user haven't interacted before for a specific type of object, then that object will never be recommended to the user.

The major disadvantage is that it is ineffective to provision recommendations for new users or new entities. The existing recommendations systems for books uses hybrid nature of recommendations category and it varies based on the application. Most of datasets are unique and each metric-based recommendation comprises of unique attributes. Recommendations are eventually structured for both online and offline based on area of application.

III. PROPOSED ALGORITHM

Methodology consists of three sections mainly A, B and C where A discusses on data gathering, preprocessing and feature extraction methods, B describes the algorithm used, working steps and specification and C discusses on model implementation and architecture.

3.1. Data pre-processing

Initially data is gathered in the form of excel file. Data consists of around 300 rows and 15 columns. Data is initially comprised with non-null values as well as null values. Later data is preprocessed for removal of null values and irrelevant data. Important and required attributes along with values are segmented into new data file in excel format for further processing of the model.

3.2. Data flow sequence

Following is the level zero data flow diagram for keyword- based recommendation engine. Initially the connection is developed between user interface and the working model. Level 0 shows that the initial flow of data from the raw input stream to processing model thereby integrated with result to output stream.

Basically, the model doesn't consist of database medium, but temporal data is stored in self-integrated database of the model and once the data is processed temporal data is made inactive and thereby user queries the engine, and the engine fetches the data from the temporal database and retrieves back the result and updates it to user by means of

user interface which is a dynamic view of result to the user.

Following Fig. 1 describes the level zero flow of recommendation engine interaction with user and model and its processing units and storage units.

Fig. 1. Level 0 Data flow diagram of the model.

The query from the user is transferred to another query format by the model so that communication between the model and processing parameters be stable and resilient. The intermediate node is the book recommendation engine which serves parallel both request as well as responses.

Level one data flow diagram is one step ahead of level zero data flow diagram. Book dataset is collected from the trusted source and the data is raw data that is data is in the form of raw data with noisy values, null values, missing values.

Initially data pre-processing is done where it is a process before data handover to the model. All the null values are either removed or arranged with other values, all the missing values are optimized, and noisy values are treated as junk and removed out of this process.

Data obtained from the data pre-processing step is pre-processed data which is free from all the un-optimized values. Next a feature is extracted throughout the model to focus on feature and develop and instance to run the model for certainty.

After feature extraction algorithm is applied to the model and algorithm is considered in such a way that it satisfies all the requirements and all the parameters that are needed for the model to process is encapsulated and those parameters are well passed to model as initial instances.

Query is requested from the user by means of user interface and that query is fed as input to the model and model responses back to user with relevant information. Result is viewed by the user by means of use interface. Without user interface the interaction between the user and model is complex to communicate.

Following Fig. 2 describes the level one flow of recommendation engine data and its overall process sequence.

Fig. 2. Level 1 Data flow sequence of the model.

3.3. Algorithm

The algorithm used for the implementation of the model is KNN that is K nearest neighbor. K-Nearest Neighbor is one of the simplest Machine Learning algorithms based on Supervised Learning technique.

This algorithm is also known as zero parameter algorithm in which no parameters is considered for processing. Even though the algorithm is non-parametric the result analysis is almost same when compared to parametric algorithm. Algorithm assumes the similarity between the new instance and past instances sometimes available instances too and posts those instances of similarities to category that is majorly likely to the available category. In other words, there is no assumption on the underlying data or with underlying data.

It is placed into subject of lazy learning process. Since this algorithm doesn't learn from the training set of data at real time or immediately it stores the required info and pulls the data whenever required. Data is pulled from temporal storage at the time of classification and specific actions are performed on them.

The steps involved in algorithm is as follows:

Step-1: Initially select the neighbors as K value that are corresponding neighbors to classification parameter or instance.

Step-2: So, the next step is to calculate the distance between the selected neighbors. Evaluation of distance enhances the algorithm to run smoother under all classification conditions. The distance that needs to be evaluated is Euclidean distance. Euclidean distance should be evaluated for selected neighbors in fact for K neighbors.

Step-3: The next step involves section of nearest data points based on calculated Euclidean distance. Choose the data points such that it is nearer to the expected instance or category parameter.

Step-4: Among all the nearer data points count all the occurrences of data points that are nearer to specified outcome in each phase. The count should be for each category.

Step-5: This step involves assign of the nearer data points to the category which was considered in the previous step for which the occurrences of the nearest neighbors statistically provision maxima that is assign the points to category which has a maximum nearer neighbor.

Step-6: Finally, the classification model is ready for the recommendation engine in order to provision relevant suggestions and information's. The Euclidean distance can be evaluated using Eq. 1 statistical method:

$$\text{Euclidean } \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^k (x_i - y_i)^2} \quad \text{Eq. (1)}$$

Where x and y are instances to be classified and k is the parameter tuning.

3.4. Model sequence flow

A sequence diagram is a graphical representation of the object with a flow serially. Following is the sequence diagram for the book recommendation engine. Initially user requests the model by means of user interface. The dataset fed to the model is initially preprocessed and all the null values and missing values are removed from the object instance. If the data after preprocessing stage consists of any sort of junky values, the model start overs the preprocessing now receiving notification of junky values.

The data after the preprocessing stage is called processed data. This processed data can be used for future enhancing for the model and thereby input to the model. The data can be split into training data and test data for ensuring faster performance and fault tolerance.

The data is split in the process of data handling. The training data is sent to the algorithm for training the algorithm. Algorithm generates the model with classification and sends the signal to the previous hashed process. The signal can be by means of acknowledging to previous processing step. The result is thereby posted to user by means of user interface. User thereby views the result through user interface. The flow is as described in the following Fig. 3 and all the flow directions are serial in nature.

Fig. 3. Sequence flow of recommendation model.

IV. EXPERIMENT AND RESULT

Fig. 4. Homepage user interface with user actions.

Above Fig. 4 is the homepage for the model. User interface is one of the important factors to obtain an interaction between user and the working model. Homepage also contains a user button on click of the user button there is a redirection to login module for existing user and signup module for the new user.

Fig. 5. Login module user interface.

Fig. 5 is the login module for the existing users. Existing users can login for further view of recommendation modules with the registered email and password. If the user forgets the password or the email, a new entry should be made using signup module.

Fig. 6. Signup module for new users.

Above Fig. 6 is the signup module for the new users. A newer entry can be made by filling the signup form as shown and further process to login module and login by means of registered email and created password.

Fig. 7. Title based recommender module.

Above Fig. 7 is the snapshot of title-based recommender module. User can enter the title of book in the input bar as shown in the Fig. 7 and on click of enter recommendations are provided by means of considering title of book and rating as a parameter to the algorithm. This layout also contains user actions such as logout for returning to homepage of the model and a redirection hyperlink to access category-based recommender module. Below Fig. 8 describes the output for the above entry of title.

You can opt these below books too

- Communication Networks
- KEEPING AHEAD CONDUCTED TECHNICAL GUIDES
- Introduction to UNIX & SHELL Programming
- Lex Yacc
- Learning PHP, My SQL and JavaScript
- Machine Learning
- Introduction to UNIX and SHELL Programming by venkateshmurthy
- Introduction to The Design and Analysis of Algorithms
- Management and Entrepreneurship
- Introduction to Personnel Software Process
- MBA GUIDE TO MICROSOFT EXCEL 2002

Fig. 8. Recommendation result snapshot for the title entry.

Above Fig. 8 is the snapshot of the title-based recommender module. The recommendations are provided in the form of list with display of only the titles of the book.

Fig. 9. User interface for category-based recommender module.

Above Fig. 9 is the snapshot of the user interface for category-based recommender module. The layout contains an input bar to enter the category of the book, dropdown with list of categories arranged in a alphabetic order, enter button to view the result, a hyperlink in the navigation bar stating category count for displaying all the categories and count of books in that specific category and a table below for recommendation result display.

On selection of category from the dropdown or enter of category in input bar the recommendations are displayed in the table with author name, rack number for location of the book and the number of people voted for the book.

Book Title	Book Authors	Book Rack	Book votecount
C++ Programming Today	Barbara Johnston	6.0	187.0
C++ programming Today With C D	Barbara Johnston	3.0	478.0
Computer Algorithms/C++	Ellis Horowitz, Sartaj Sahani & Saragullavar R	1.0	384.0
Computer Concept and C Programming	Vikas Gupta	1.0	444.0
Fundamentals of Computers in C language	Rajaram	4.0	467.0
Fundamentals of Data Structures in C++	Ellis Horowitz, Sartaj Sahani, Mehta	4.0	436.0
Fundamentals of Data Structures in C	Ellis Horowitz, Sartaj Sahani, Susan Anderspm freder	4.0	484.0
Object Oriented Programming With C++	Sourav Sahay	2.0	483.0
Problem Solving with C	Jaqueline Alonzo and Keith Harrow	4.0	449.0
PROGRAMMING ANSI C 4E	E BALAGURU SWAMY	2.0	120.0

Fig. 10. Output snapshot for category-based recommender module.

Above Fig. 10 is the snapshot for the correct category. The recommendations are provided by considering category and vote count in the data as parameters for the algorithm. Based on requirements periodic vote count measures can be modified to enhance recommendations to the users.

If the user enters the wrong category a popup message is displayed stating wrong category and user needs to enter the category that are in the list of model categories popup is triggered.

Fig. 11. Snapshot of wrong category input.

Above Fig. 11 is the snapshot of the pop up encountered when a wrong entry is processed. When a user enters the category that is not in the list of model categories popup is triggered.

BOOK CATEGORY	NUMBER OF BOOKS AVAILABLE
AI	1
ARM	2
ATC	2
BIG DATA	5
C PROGRAMMING	18
CG	3
CLOUD COMPUTING	5
COMPUTER ORGANIZATION	4

Fig. 12. Snapshot of list of categories and count of books in each category.

Fig. 12 is the snapshot of categories and their count of available books. In the category-based recommender module layout there is a hyperlink to redirect to this page. User gets an overview of all available categories.

V.CONCLUSION AND FUTURE ENHANCEMENTS

Recommendation engines are one in which provides overall customization and optimizations. Apart from search engines recommendation engines provide relevant information only but recommendation is provided to extent up to which recommendation parameter is defined and declared. The data from the source was too small to perform the model and model with algorithm specified here cannot overcome with less data. So, when data is less in extent model behaves in a different manner when compared to model with larger datasets. There are two types of recommendation engines that is content based, and collaborative based, these two are efficient in their own way one storing past information's for recommendations and another storing mandatory parameters and providing relevant suggestions to the user. The ultimate moto is that to provide suggestions or in a clear way recommend based on user input. A hybrid nature of both types of recommendation filters can be uses based on certain use cases so that stability increases, and relevant data is obtained at all the use case scenarios.

Future enhancements carry deployment of web application to android-based application which is compatible with all versions, addition of books and its categories for enhancing recommendation engine, User feedback area for users to give the feedback and rating to specific book which can model.

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